

METHODS OF RESEARCHING THE FORMATION OF VOLITIONAL QUALITIES IN STUDENTS

Hamrayeva Oynisa Farxod kizi

Teacher of the Department of Pedagogy of Fergana State University

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Abstract. *Volitional activity directs a person's actions based on the essence of the prospective goals he sets for himself as a conscious person in relation to existence. A person should pay attention to his exemplary ideals, his guiding ideas, beliefs, views, evaluations he gives to himself and other people, the adequacy of evaluation criteria, so that they do not create disproportionate wishes, desires, and wishes in relation to the criteria. , seeks to slow them down or completely eliminate them.*

Keywords: *Volitional process always invites a person to be active, leads him to set a firm path or direction, directs him to steady action, prevents negative feelings such as hesitation and doubt.*

INTRODUCTION. Volitional activity directs a person's actions based on the essence of the prospective goals he sets for himself as a conscious person in relation to existence. A person should pay attention to his exemplary ideals, his guiding ideas, beliefs, views, evaluations he gives to himself and other people, the adequacy of evaluation criteria, so that they do not create disproportionate wishes, desires, and wishes in relation to the criteria. , seeks to slow them down or completely eliminate them. At this point, it is appropriate to emphasize that volitional activity performs priority functions of a certain level in human behavior. These functions, firstly, increase the quality level of the implementation of the behavior of the individual, secondly, they create conditions for finding solutions to problems of various characteristics, which are of great importance for human life and personal activity, and thirdly, the essence of the problem of human personality provides access, fourthly, it serves to coordinate the action of a voluntary act.

The function of controlling voluntary behavior is not only to regulate the speed of limiting the desire, movement and aspiration to a certain level, but also to direct the personal activity of a person in a certain direction, It consists in increasing the strength of one's actions, aligning things and events with a common goal.

Volitional process always invites a person to be active, leads him to set a firm path or direction, directs him to steady action, prevents negative feelings such as hesitation and doubt. A goal-oriented behavior, an aspiration intended to be realized, a good intention realized, a desire instills a sense of self-confidence in a person, directs him to take bold actions, is active in the pursuit of dreams. forms an inclination. The extraordinary achievement and success of a person ensures the stability of every voluntary action, accelerates the selection, sorting, decision-making of actions, the creation of a personal style, facilitates the implementation of new voluntary actions, the subject's own volition prepares a thorough foundation for the improvement of qualities, forms the skills of applying actions that require voluntary effort to practice, social life. This spiritual process, both in renewed and unrenewed form, is manifested only through the struggle of motives, through willful effort, overcoming obstacles and difficulties.

As we mentioned above, analyzing the indicators of the formation of voluntary qualities in students, paying serious attention to its specific psychological factors, is of great importance in

ensuring the social and psychological development of the student. From this point of view, in order to have detailed information about students' determination, resilience and resistance to difficulties, separate studies were conducted on them, empirical data collection and analysis of its results based on social psychological requirements. was folded. In this paragraph, it is intended to describe the analysis of the empirical data obtained by introducing more scientific clarifications to this issue.

We will proceed to the analysis of the preliminary results obtained through the "Methodology for the Study of Voluntary Qualities of a Person" proposed by M. Chumakov, selected based on the goals and tasks of our initial research.

Analysis of the preliminary results obtained through the "Methodology for the Study of Personal Volitional Qualities" (n=310)

Name of scales	Average(M)		Differences s
	2- course n=170	4- course n=140	
Responsibility	11,2	14,1	-3,2*
Initiative	16,5	13,3	-3,4*
Courage	10,1	12,6	-2,2*
Independence	12,4	14,3	-2,4*
Fortitude	11,1	13,0	-2,5*
Persistence	9,6	12,9	-2,4*
Enthusiasm	12,5	10,1	-2,2*
Attention	13,1	13,7	-1,2
Pursuit of the goal	14,5	15,1	-1,2

Results Significant differences were noted according to the analysis of the preliminary results obtained by the method of studying the will qualities of a person. Including "responsibility" (t=3.2; p≤0.05), "initiative" (t=3.4; p≤0.05), "courage" (t=2.2; p≤0.05), "independence" (t=2.4; p≤0.05), "perseverance" (t=2.5; p≤0.05), "persistence" (t=2.4; p≤0.05) and "enthusiasm" (t=2.2; p≤0.05) factors were observed.

Significant differences were observed on the initial "responsibility" factor of the methodology (t=3.2; p≤0.05). In particular, the students of the 4th level were found to have patience, to diligently fulfill their obligations both in studies and at work, responsibility, and to think and make a decision before starting a job.

According to the next "initiative" factor, students of the 2nd stage scored higher than students of the 4th stage (t=3.4; p≤0.05). This indicates that students of the 2nd level usually do not have difficulty speaking in front of others, strive for leadership, always arrive on time for studies and important meetings, can focus on one point for a long time, always carry out work according to a plan, make decisions quickly. ability to accept, and it was observed that the mood of optimism was formed more than pessimism.

According to the "Courage" factor, the 4th grade students had a high result (t=2.2; p≤0.05). In particular, it was proved that they have the ability to make quick decisions, complete the given tasks on time, high self-confidence, the ability to set specific and clear goals, and the high risk-taking nature.

There is a significant difference in the "Independence" factor, and students of the 4th grade scored higher ($t=2.4$; $p\leq 0.05$). This indicates that students of the 4th level have a responsibility and a free approach to the assigned tasks, the ability to solve problems independently, and starting with the most important depending on the level of importance before doing something.

Significant differences were also observed in terms of the "perseverance" factor, and the students of the 4th stage showed a higher result than the students of the 2nd stage ($t=2.5$; $p\leq 0.05$). In particular, patience in difficult situations, engaging in one activity for a long time, resistance to difficulties and striving for goals were found in them.

Students of the 4th stage recorded a high result on the next "firmness" factor ($t=2.4$; $p\leq 0.05$). It was found that they have high goal-striving, repeated efforts even if they cannot do something at the first attempt, striving to create something new, and diligently fulfilling their obligations.

Significant differences were also observed on the "Enthusiasm" factor, and the students of the 2nd stage recorded a higher result than the students of the 4th stage. In particular, students of the 2nd stage were able to finish the assigned work despite the difficulties, always have activeness in any activity, always join the team's opinion and always work in consultation with others.

The more a person strives for a goal, the more he needs to be firm in moving towards his goal. A person who knows how to set a goal for himself, who moves towards his goal, also shows determination by making a strong will. Therefore, connections between the two criteria have been identified. The absence of connections among the remaining criteria means that determination itself is based on will qualities. There is a significant difference in the factor "Independence", students of the 4th grade recorded a high result ($t=2.4$; $p\leq 0.05$). This indicates that students of the 4th level have a responsibility and a free approach to the assigned tasks, the ability to solve problems independently, and starting with the most important depending on the level of importance before doing something.

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Significant differences were also observed on the "Enthusiasm" factor, and the students of the 2nd stage recorded a higher result than the students of the 4th stage. In particular, students of the 2nd stage were able to finish the assigned work despite the difficulties, always have activeness in any activity, always join the team's opinion and always work in consultation with others. It is observed that there is a significant ontogenetic relationship between situational reflection and persistence. Based on empirical data, it can be said that it is important for a person with situational reflexes to achieve results in the same situation today, and it does not require the development of willpower. It is worth noting that along with the development of all types of voluntary qualities in a person, we can see that qualities such as independence, criticality, initiative, and meaningfulness are also fully developed in voluntary effort. Because the work and activities performed by this category of people are effective they have the self-awareness and self-management skills to do so.

No significant correlations were observed among the remaining indicators. In this case, the level of retrospective and prospective reflection of determination was not important.

According to the results of the investigation, it was observed that situational, retrospective and future activity, that is, perspective reflection has a significant relationship with self-management. At this point, it should be said that in most cases, the development of the highest form of human mental activity requires a rational solution to any problem and situation. But from the results of the experiment, it can be concluded that all types of conscious self-management must be developed in people who have formed reflexes for future activities. The fact that there is a high positive relationship with self-sufficiency in cooperation with others and interpersonal relationships in the group of test subjects indicates that a person controls his own behavior.

Personal volitional qualities have a special connection with self-control. In fact, self-management develops on the basis of voluntary qualities. In particular, the correlation between the courage scale and self-control was determined in our subjects. This, in turn, means that an increase in courage leads to an increase in self-control. Volitional process always invites a person to be active, leads him to set a firm path or direction, directs him to steady action, prevents negative feelings such as hesitation and doubt. Goal-oriented behavior, aspiration intended to be realized, a good intention realized, a desire instills a sense of self-confidence in a person, directs him to take bold actions, is active in the pursuit of dreams. forms an inclination. The extraordinary achievement and success of a person ensures the stability of every voluntary action, accelerates the selection, sorting, decision-making of actions, the creation of a personal style, facilitates the implementation of new voluntary actions, the subject's own volition prepares a thorough basis for the improvement of qualities, forms the skills of applying actions that require voluntary effort to practice, social life.

Courage is the willpower shown to overcome doubts and hesitations, as well as timely decision-making. Therefore, it is important for a person to manage himself in various situations and to make the necessary decisions quickly and control his emotions. Correlation between mindfulness scale and self-control was also determined. This indicates that if a person has a high level of attention to his environment and relatives, and his activities, then he

management, voluntary control will also be high. The fact that there are no connections between the remaining criteria is due to the fact that voluntary qualities have an important place in all aspects of the internal regulation of a person. It is known that human relations and cooperative activities are distinguished by the fact that every person has the ability to think, reflect, and reason. From this point of view, a person's relationships with others are explained by the fact that they contain the characteristics of reflexivity along with the development of self-management. Also, if we pay attention to the results of the test subjects, it was found that they always have a high level of self-awareness, analysis and management in the process of working in cooperation with others. It was determined that this always depends on the development of the individual's conscious self-management in the process of human behavior and activity. At this point, measures were taken to study the relationship between the directions of reflexivity and self-management of personality development in order to fulfill the tasks put forward in our dissertation. In addition, the level of perspective reflection is characterized by the ability of the examinees to plan the future of their activities, to foresee life-related situations, to make social decisions, and to be oriented towards the future. According to the results of correlative divisions between the method of studying voluntary qualities of a person and voluntary self-control, the factor "Persistence" is

combined with "Responsibility", "Independence" and "Strength towards the goal", " Positive correlations with the factor "Self-management" and "Courage" and "Attention" were noted.

The results of the research on the manifestation of voluntary qualities in a person show that voluntary qualities are psychological characteristics that cause various obstacles in a person's activity, and it was determined that these factors can cause the emergence of voluntary qualities in them.

According to the results of correlational divisions between manifestation of reflection levels and volitional self-control, the factor "Persistence" is related to "Situational reflection", the factor "Self-control" is related to "Situational reflection", "Retrospective reflection" and "Perspective reflection" positive connections were noted.

Conclusion according to the results of correlative divisions between the method of studying voluntary qualities of a person and voluntary self-control, the factor "Persistence" is combined with "Responsibility", "Independence" and "Strength towards the goal", " Positive correlations with the factor "Self-management" and "Courage" and "Attention" were noted.

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REERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Tanqidiy tahlil, qat'iy tartib-intizom va shaxsiy javobgarlik – har bir rahbar faoliyatning kundalik qoidasi bo'lishi kerak. –T., 2017. –B. 45.
2. Olimov.L.Ya., Maxmudova.Z.M. Psixologicheskiye mexanizmy deviantnogo povedeniya. Psixologiya XXI veka. –Yaroslavl., 2020. –S. 125-127.
2. Shamshetova.A.K., Melibayeva R.N., Usmanova X.E., Xaydarov I.O. Umumiy psixologiya, O'quv qo'llanma. –Toshkent, 2018.
3. Bekmirov.R. Shaxsning emotsional irodaviy holatlari. –Toshkent, 2002.
4. Olimov L.Ya., Baratov Sh.R., Avezov O.R. Psixologiya nazariyasi va tarixi. Darslik. –T.: "O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati" nashriyoti. 2019. –B. 494.; Olimov L.Ya. Shaxs psixologiyasi. "Durдона" nashriyoti. –Buxoro, 2019.
5. Olimov.L.Ya., Maxmudova.Z.M. O'smirlarda psixologik himoya mexanizmlarining namoyon bo'lishining o'ziga xosligi. XXI asr psixologiyasi...
6. E.G'oziyev Umumiy psixologiya darslik I-kitob. Toshkent. "Universitet" 2022
7. Hamrayeva.O.F. (2023). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASASI TALABALARINI KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING AYRIM JIHLTLARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(1), 537-544.
8. O.F.Hamrayeva,Sh.Ibrohimov. (2023). PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AND WAYS OF ITS DEVELOPMENT. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(12), 760–761. Retrieved from <https://www.eijmr.org/index.php/eijmr/article/view/834>
9. O.F.Hamrayeva, & Ibrohimova Shahnoza Shuhratjon qizi. (2023). ALISHER NAVOIYNING ASARLARIDA TA'LIM TARBIYA MASALALARI. *THEORY OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCHES OF WHOLE WORLD*, 3(3), 49–53. Retrieved from <https://esiconf.com/index.php/TOSROWW/article/view/599>

10. Hamroyeva.O.F. (2023). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASASI TALABALARINI KASBIY-KOMUNIKATIV KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(4), 985-991.
11. Abdixakimovich.X.K. (2023). PEDAGOGIK HAMKORLIK ASOSIDA BO'LAJAK OFITSERLARDA FUQAROLIK KOMPETENSIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH. *Science and innovation*, 2(Special Issue 12), 538-541.
12. Ergasheva.N.M. (2023). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTI RAHBARLARINING KOGNITIV KOMPETENTLIGI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(11), 697-702
13. O.F.Hamrayeva, & Bozorova Fotimaxon Jo'rabek qizi. (2023). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASASI TALABALARIDA AXLOQIY VA ESTETIK TARBIYANI RIVOJLANTIRISH. *MODERN PROBLEMS IN EDUCATION AND THEIR SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*, 7(7), 9–12. Retrieved from <https://esiconf.com/index.php/mpe/article/view/598>
14. O.F.Hamrayeva, & Nozimova Dilfuza Jahongir qizi. (2023). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASLARI TALABALARIDA FUQOROLIK TARBIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH. *THEORY OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCHES OF WHOLE WORLD*, 3(3), 45–48. Retrieved from <https://esiconf.com/index.php/TOSROWW/article/view/595>
15. file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/mamun-2023-1-26.pdf